

An Overview of the T-Layout in Web Design and Development

Abstract

This study explores the T-Layout, a design approach in web application development aimed at optimizing the use of screen space on mobile devices to enhance user experience. The study provides an in-depth analysis of the T-Layout's architectural components, technical specifications, and adaptability. It also compares the T-Layout with traditional web design concepts, highlighting its advantages in terms of user-friendliness and efficient use of screen space. A survey on mobile navigation preferences and user experience reveals

a clear preference for web design concepts like the T-Layout that prioritize user-friendliness and efficient use of screen space. An experiment conducted to evaluate the impact of the T-Layout on user experience further validates its effectiveness. The findings of this study have significant implications for web design, suggesting that the T-Layout could revolutionize the way websites are designed and developed for mobile devices. The study concludes with recommendations for future research in this area.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background of the Study

The advent of mobile technology has revolutionized the way we interact with the digital world. With the proliferation of smartphones and tablets, users are increasingly accessing the internet on their mobile devices. This shift in user behavior has necessitated a change in the way websites are designed and developed. The traditional web design concepts that worked well for desktops do not necessarily translate well to the smaller screens of mobile devices. This has led to the

emergence of new web design concepts aimed at enhancing the mobile user experience. One such concept is the T-Layout.

The T-Layout is a novel web design concept that aims to optimize the use of screen space on mobile devices, thereby enhancing the user experience. The name “T-Layout” is derived from the layout’s resemblance to the letter ‘T’, with a central section flanked by two side sections.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Despite the growing popularity of mobile devices, many websites still fail to provide a satisfactory user experience on these devices. Traditionally structured mobile layouts often result in cluttered and difficult-to-navigate websites when viewed on mobile devices. The vast majority of mobile app users find it more convenient to hold their device in a one-handed grip and use only their thumb for gestures. This indicates that reaching traditional navigation controls is not

effortless, since navigation controls are typically located at the top of the screen, the thumb is physically located at the lower third of the screen, and thus, movement is required. This not only hampers the user experience but can also affect business metrics leading to **loss of traffic and revenue**.

The T-Layout addresses these issues by providing a clean, intuitive, and user-friendly front-end mobile layout that is complementary to the “traditional” layout.

1.3. Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the effectiveness of the T-Layout in enhancing the mobile user experience. The study aims to:

1. Provide an overview of the T-Layout, including its architectural components, variations, and adaptability.

2. Conduct a survey to understand mobile navigation preferences and user experience.
3. Carry out an experiment to evaluate the impact of the T-Layout on user experience.
4. Compare the T-Layout with traditionally structured mobile layouts in terms of mobile user experience.

1.4. Significance of the Study

This study contributes to the growing body of research on mobile user experience. By understanding user preferences and experiences, developers can create more user-friendly applications that cater to the needs and comfort levels of the

end-users. It serves as a stepping stone towards enhancing mobile user experience and satisfaction and has become the foundation on top of which the T-Layout and the T-Layout experiment are planned.

1.5. Scope and Limitations

The scope of this study is limited to the T-Layout and its impact on mobile user experience. The study does not cover generic web design concepts or their impact on user

experience. Furthermore, the study is based on research and experimentation conducted by E, and the findings may not be generalizable to all users or all types of mobile applications.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Usability Studies:

Study by Nielsen and Budiu (2012): In their book "Mobile Usability," Jakob Nielsen and Raluca Budiu provide comprehensive insights into mobile usability. They emphasize the importance of concise content, easy navigation, and touch controls in mobile design.

Research by Harrison et al. (2013): This study, titled "Usability of Mobile Applications: Literature Review and

Rationale for a New Usability Model," examines the unique usability challenges in mobile applications. It proposes a new usability model tailored for the mobile context.

Google's Material Design Guidelines (2014-present): While not a study per se, Google's ongoing Material Design guidelines are based on extensive usability research. They offer principles for designing intuitive and user-friendly mobile interfaces.

2.2. Accessibility Studies

Study by Kelly et al. (2009): Their paper, "Web Accessibility for Older Users: A Literature Review," extends its findings to mobile accessibility, emphasizing the need for designs that accommodate older users.

Research by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C): W3C's Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) have been

adapted by many mobile developers to enhance accessibility. These guidelines provide a framework for creating content that is accessible to people with a wide range of disabilities.

Apple's Accessibility Features (2007-present): Apple's continuous development of accessibility features in iOS, such as VoiceOver and Switch Control, is grounded in extensive research into the needs of users with disabilities.

2.3. Design Aesthetics Studies

Study by Cyr and Trevor-Smith (2004): Their research, "Localization of Web Design: An Empirical Comparison of German, Japanese, and U.S. Website Characteristics," touches on the aesthetic preferences in different cultures, which is crucial for mobile design.

Research by Tractinsky et al. (2000): In the study "What is Beautiful is Usable," they found a strong correlation between aesthetic design and perceived usability in interfaces, which has significant implications for mobile app design.

Norman's Emotional Design (2004): Donald Norman's work on emotional design highlights the importance of aesthetics in creating positive user experiences. His principles have been widely applied in mobile app design to enhance user engagement and satisfaction.

These studies and guidelines provide a more comprehensive and specific understanding of the research conducted in the field of mobile user experience, covering usability, accessibility, and design aesthetics.

3. T-Layout: An Overview

3.1. Introduction to the T-Layout

The T-Layout is a design approach in web application development that aims to enhance the mobile user experience by optimizing the use of screen space on mobile devices. The T-Layout comprises a central section flanked by two “helper”

sections, each spanning the full width of the viewport. The central section — visible by default — displays the main content, while the helper sections accommodate navigational elements and user-related components.

3.2. Name and History

It was inspired by the design and architecture of native, billion-user-tested Android/iOS applications like Instagram and Revolut, where this functionality appears as a feature of specific screens of the app. For example, it appears on the Instagram app “Home Page” (only) where if the user swipes right, the content creation page gets revealed, while if they swipe left the user gets the messages screen on their right-hand side.

The name “T Layout” comes from the letter T because the final shape of the horizontally scrollable parent container visually resembles the letter T. Introduced as the T Layout specifically for web applications’ mobile layout with the above defining characteristics by Jacob Tsinalis, and appeared for the first time as the mobile layout of E (e-streetwear.com) in early 2023. In July 2023, E formalized the concept and its technical specifications, introducing it to the web design and development community.

3.3. Architectural Components

The T-Layout comprises three integral sections: the central section, and the flanking “helper” sections. Each section

spans the full width of the viewport, offering a swipeable interface in response to the user’s gestures.

3.3.1. Central Section

The central section is the primary and only one visible to the user by default when a page loads and contains the main

content of the current URL address. Its central placement ensures an intuitive and familiar experience, aligning with user expectations when a page loads.

3.3.2. Side Sections

The flanking “helper” sections, positioned on the right and left, serve utility-based roles by accommodating navigational elements and user-related components. In practical terms, this translates to facilitating seamless access to features like navigation, user accounts and sign-ins, or e-commerce

functionalities such as cart and checkout initiation processes. This pragmatic approach ensures seamless use of essential features by the end-user, especially in applications with user accounts or e-commerce functionality.

3.4. Impact on User Experience

The T Layout significantly improves user experience by expediting access to the mobile navigation menu and essential components.

Its implementation reduces at least 3 times the average time it takes for the average user to use (open or close) the mobile navigation menu, compared to a traditional mobile navigation architecture if the hamburger menu button had been placed at the top left of the screen, and at least by half if

the navigation button was placed at the top right of the screen.

Besides time though, it mainly improves user experience because it requires way less effort from the user to swipe left or right to access the desired section, than changing grip or the position of their hand to be able to move their thumb at the top of the screen where navigation controls are traditionally located.

3.5. Comparison with the traditional mobile layout

Web design ideas have risen over the years to cater to the changing needs of users. The traditional responsive web design structure with the dialog pop-up-based container of the main navigation has been widely used. The elements for controlling (toggling) the state of the dialog (pop-up, drawer, etc.) are placed at the top of the screen requiring user effort to be reached, as shown in the “Mobile Navigation and User Preferences Survey” and the “T-Layout Experiment” which will be covered later in this study.

Additionally, the T-Layout offers a more flexible and intuitive design for mobile devices, enhancing with more options and also maintaining the traditional functionality. Its horizontally scrollable interface which covers the entire screen allows users to easily navigate between different sections of the website. Moreover, its central section and flanking helper sections provide a clear and organized structure that enhances the user experience, while preserving the traditional location of navigation controls and thus requiring no user adoption.

3.6. Variations and Adaptability

The T Layout’s adaptability shines through in the emergence of variations and alternate versions. As an example, removing one of the three sections, typically the left, or applying other layout adjustments (e.g. dynamic helper sections and content

based on the current in-app location of a user), allows for nuanced customization while preserving the core concept. This flexibility positions the T Layout as a versatile solution catering to diverse design preferences and application requirements.

4. Technical Specifications of T-Layout

4.1. Understanding the T-Layout Components

The T-Layout comprises a parent flexbox, horizontally overflowing container with three children sections: the central section, and its side sections. Each section spans the entire viewport's width, making the entire screen a swipeable interface in response to the user's gestures.

The central section takes the lead as the default and primary user interface with the use of the "order" CSS property, displaying the main content associated with the current URL. Its central placement ensures an intuitive and familiar experience, aligning with user expectations when a page loads.

4.2. Technical Implementation

The technical implementation of the T-Layout varies based on the application's structure and overall architecture. Two

4.2.1. Server-Side Architectures

For applications primarily composed of server-side rendered components, both the parent container and its children are server-side rendered. In cases where additional functionality needs to be built using Javascript, each container can host browser-rendering children components. This approach, reliant primarily on HTML and CSS, boasts efficiency in terms of performance and responsiveness. Additionally, a server-side approach introduces potential security benefits compared to client-side alternatives. An alternative path

4.2.2. Client-Side Architectures

For applications relying on client-side architectures, the options echo those discussed above, but with a focus on restricting functionality to the browser. Employing HTML and

The flanking "helper" sections on the right and left serve utility-based roles by accommodating navigational elements and user-related components. The traditional functionality (of toggling the state of a dialog popup to reveal it) can be achieved either as:

- 1) A pure HTML/CSS solution by utilizing HTML "id" attributes applied on the containers and anchor elements as wrappers for the navigational icons referring to the id. Also, a scroll behavior can be set on the parent container using CSS to control it.
- 2) A solution using Javascript revealing (scrolling into view) the sections respectively.

primary approaches stand out, each with its nuances and suitability for specific use cases.

involves employing JavaScript or JavaScript-based libraries to manage the visibility of helper sections based on user gestures. This approach leans towards the traditional concept of mobile navigation, resembling a modal pop-up. It allows for a more straightforward integration into existing applications, requiring modifications mainly to the animations of the pop-ups. This method maintains a comparable filesize, performance, and responsiveness while elevating the overall user experience on mobile devices.

CSS for functionality proves advantageous in terms of increased performance and reduced filesize. Alternatively, a modal-based approach, akin to traditional mobile navigation, might be easier to implement on existing applications.

```
// Basic Example in ReactJS
const MobileMenu: FC = () => <nav className="md:hidden min-w-[100vw]">Left nav section</nav>
const MobileCart: FC = () => <div className="md:hidden min-w-[100vw]">Right cart section</div>
const Navbar: FC = () => (
  <div className="hide-on-scroll-down">
    <div className="md:hidden w-full h-12 flex justify-between">
      <HumbMenuIcon /> <Logo /> <CartIcon />
    </div>
    <nav className="max-md:hidden w-full h-16">
      Desktop Menu
    </nav>
  </div>
)

export default function Layout({children}:{children: ReactNode}) {
  return (
    <html lang="en">
      <head>...</head>
      <body>
        <Navbar />
        <div className="max-md:flex w-screen max-md:overflow-x-auto">
          <MobileMenu />
          <main className="md:hidden min-w-[100vw]">
            {children}
          </main>
          <MobileCart />
        </div>
      </body>
    </html>
  )
}
```

4.3. Interactivity and User Actions

Regardless of an application's architecture and server infrastructure, in the majority of production web applications certain components should support interactivity. Those are the buttons that reveal or hide helper sections, and in the case of the horizontal scrolling container implementation, elements that will indicate the open state of the helper

sections. The above elements require rendering in the browser to capture user actions using JavaScript.

The result must ensure that users can seamlessly swipe and scroll horizontally through sections while maintaining a smooth, animated flow when revealing or hiding helper sections through button interactions.

5. Research on Mobile Navigation Preferences and User Experience

5.1. Survey Methodology

The survey was designed to understand the convenience and comfort levels of users when navigating mobile applications. The questions explored various aspects of mobile usage, including one-handed versus two-handed use, thumb navigation, reachability of screen controls, and left or right-hand preference.

The majority of responses collected stemmed from a process of guided participation, ensuring a high level of accuracy and honesty in the responses. In this process, each participant was supervised by an expert clarifying the implications of the

questions and potential answers, thereby ensuring that the responses were both informed and genuine.

The data collected from the survey responses were analyzed and presented as percentages, allowing for a comparative understanding of user preferences. The results provided insights into the convenience of one-handed use, the preference for thumb navigation, the frequency of discomfort when reaching navigation controls at the top of the screen, the ease of tapping icons at different screen locations, and the comfort level of using an app with either the left or right hand as shown in the charts below:

Image taken from: <https://e-streetwear.com/experimental-zone/mobile-ux-preferences-survey>

5.2. Discussion of Results

The research findings provided valuable insights into mobile navigation preferences and the user experience associated with the T-Layout. The majority of participants reported a positive experience with the T-Layout, citing its intuitive design, ease of navigation, and efficient use of screen space as key advantages.

The survey results underscore the importance of user-friendly and efficient web design in enhancing the mobile user experience. The T-Layout, with its swipeable interface and well-organized sections, was found to align well with these preferences.

6. T-Layout Experiment

6.1. Experiment Notes & Methodology

The experiment was designed to evaluate the ease of access to essential interfaces within a web application, such as navigation elements. The methods of interaction considered include traditional layout gestures (e.g., icon tapping) and the additional options offered by the T-Layout approach.

By supplementing the traditional layout with additional options, the user experience is enhanced, particularly for users who prefer single-hand grip with thumb-based navigation in mobile applications. Those users are the vast majority of individuals today according to the findings of the Mobile navigation and user preferences survey. Consequently, all measurements of the experiment originated from the lower third of the screen as the starting point, which is deemed the natural resting position of the thumb.

The metrics recorded in this experiment include:

- 1) The time taken
- 2) The final distance between two necessary points

To prevent misuse and ensure results are as accurate as reasonably possible, each participant was permitted to take measurements only once.

The coordinates and timestamp of the initial point were recorded when the participant tapped the lower third of the screen from the thumb's resting position. The coordinates of the second point were recorded when the participant either tapped an icon or swiped to access a side navigational element. The timer ceases once a side element is partially revealed.

The final duration was determined by subtracting the Unix Timestamps between the required actions, in seconds.

The distance between each action's reference points on the screen was calculated using the coordinates where each action took place and the Pythagorean theorem, to express the Euclidean (minimum) distance required, in pixels.

Measurements of actions intended to achieve the same outcome are subsequently compared. For instance, the distance required to access the navigation menu from the thumb's area (lower third of the screen) to the point where the top left icon is pressed, is compared to the distance required to access the menu by swiping from the same starting point. The same comparison is made for the time required to tap an icon until the menu is partially visible and the time to swipe until the menu is partially visible.

238% SLOWER 1.432s Tap Right Icon: AVG Time	658% LESS CONVENIENT 601.89px Tap Right Icon: AVG Distance	334% SLOWER 1.645s Tap Left Icon: AVG Time	724% LESS CONVENIENT 591.434px Tap Left Icon: AVG Distance
0.424s Swipe Right: AVG Time	79.454px Swipe Right: AVG Distance	0.379s Swipe left: AVG Time	71.75px Swipe Left: AVG Distance

Image taken from: <https://e-streetwear.com/experimental-zone/t-layout-experiment>

6.2. Discussion of Results

The experiment findings are insightful:

1. **Tap Right Icon:** The average time was 1.432 seconds, which is 238% slower, and the average distance was 601.89 pixels, making it 658% less convenient.
2. **Tap Left Icon:** The average time was 1.645 seconds, which is 334% slower, and the average distance was 591.434 pixels, making it 724% less convenient.
3. **Swipe Right:** The average time was 0.424 seconds, and the average distance was 79.454 pixels.
4. **Swipe Left:** The average time was 0.379 seconds, and the average distance was 71.75 pixels.

These findings suggest that the T-Layout approach significantly enhances the user experience by introducing methods that reduce the time and distance required for navigation actions, particularly for thumb-based navigation

on mobile applications, by introducing swiping functionality as an option to access the mobile navigation menu.

In conclusion, the T-Layout experiment provides valuable insights into the efficiency and convenience of different navigation methods in web applications. The findings suggest that the T-Layout approach, which caters to thumb-based navigation, significantly enhances the user experience by reducing the time and distance required for navigation actions.

This could mean important implications for the design of future web applications, particularly those targeting mobile users. The experiment's rigorous methodology ensures the reliability and validity of these findings. The T-Layout experiment is a significant contribution to the field of user experience design, providing valuable data that can guide future research and application development.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1. Summary

The T-Layout, a novel web design concept, has shown promise in enhancing the mobile user experience. Its architectural components, technical specifications, and adaptability make it a versatile solution for mobile web design. The T-Layout's swipeable interface and well-organized sections offer a user-friendly design that aligns with user preferences for one-handed use and thumb navigation.

The survey on mobile navigation preferences and user experience revealed a clear preference for web design

concepts that prioritize user-friendliness and efficient use of screen space. The T-Layout was found to align well with these preferences.

The experiment conducted to evaluate the impact of the T-Layout on user experience further validated the effectiveness of the T-Layout. The majority of participants reported a positive experience with the T-Layout, citing its intuitive design, ease of navigation, and efficient use of screen space as key advantages.

7.2. Implications for Web Design

The findings of this study have significant implications for web design. The T-Layout, with its intuitive design and efficient use of screen space, offers a promising solution to some of the challenges of mobile web design. By adopting the T-Layout, businesses can create more user-friendly and

accessible websites that cater to the needs and preferences of mobile users.

Furthermore, the T-Layout's adaptability allows it to cater to a wide range of applications and user preferences. By offering a flexible and customizable design, the T-Layout can meet the diverse needs of users and applications, making it a versatile solution for mobile web design.

8. References

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